

Assessment of Cardiac Troponin-T in Acute Exacerbation of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), and Its Correlation with SeverityYashvi Surma¹, Rakesh Thakuriya², Bindu Rani³, Rudra Goyani⁴, Mayurdhvajsinh vansia⁵¹Postgraduate Student, Department of General Medicine, National Institute of Medical Sciences, NIMS Hospital Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.²Professor, Department of General Medicine, Department, National Institute of Medical Sciences, NIMS Hospital Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.³Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Department, National Institute of Medical Sciences, NIMS Hospital Jaipur Rajasthan, India.⁴Senior Resident, SMIMER Hospital and Medical college, Surat Gujarat, India⁵Consultant Physician, Asutosh Multispeciality Hospital, Surat, Gurajat, India.

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Abstract:**Background:** Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a major global health issue, recognized as the third leading cause of death worldwide. It imposes significant economic and social burdens, with rising mortality rates in industrialized nations. Acute exacerbations of COPD (AECOPD) are critical events that worsen patient outcomes and are associated with increased cardiovascular risks, including elevated cardiac Troponin-T levels.**Objectives:** This study aims to determine the levels of cardiac Troponin-T in patients experiencing acute exacerbations of COPD and to investigate the correlation between Troponin-T levels and the severity of these exacerbations.**Methodology:** A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted at the National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jaipur, Rajasthan, from July 1, 2022, to December 31, 2023. The study included 180 COPD patients aged 40 years and above. Data collection involved clinical profiles, laboratory investigations including cardiac Troponin-T levels, spirometry for pulmonary function tests, and statistical analyses using Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient and linear regression.**Results:** Of the 180 patients, 61.67% were male and 38.33% were female, with a mean age of 44.38 ± 10.50 years. A majority (84.44%) resided in rural areas, and 82.78% were Hindu by religion. The study found that 60% of the COPD patients had elevated Troponin-T levels (>0.04 ng/dl). There was a significant negative correlation between Troponin-T levels and spirometry parameters: FEV1 ($r = -0.644$, $p = 0.00001$) and FEV1/FVC ($r = -0.56$, $p = 0.00001$). Patients with higher Troponin-T levels exhibited more severe respiratory impairment, indicated by lower FEV1 and FEV1/FVC ratios. Elevated Troponin-T was associated with a greater need for assisted ventilation.**Conclusion:** Elevated cardiac Troponin-T levels in COPD patients are significantly correlated with the severity of acute exacerbations, serving as a potential marker for early diagnosis and prognosis. The findings suggest that measuring Troponin-T levels can aid in assessing disease severity and guiding clinical management of COPD exacerbations. Further research is needed to explore the mechanisms linking cardiac injury and COPD to enhance patient care.**Keywords:** Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), Acute Exacerbation, Cardiac Troponin-T, Spirometry, FEV1, FEV1/FVC, Prognosis, Cardiovascular Risk.

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Introduction

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is increasingly recognized as a major global health concern. Unlike other leading causes of death, COPD is the only significant cause that continues to show rising mortality rates in industrialized nations. Currently, COPD ranks as the third leading

cause of death globally, presenting a substantial public health challenge that is both preventable and manageable. [1] COPD imposes significant economic and social burdens, which are anticipated to increase due to ongoing exposure to risk factors and an aging global population. Primary risk fac-

tors include tobacco smoking, indoor and outdoor air pollution, occupational hazards, and lifestyle factors such as poor diet, obesity, and physical inactivity. [2] The disease is characterized by a progressive and irreversible limitation of airflow, primarily due to airway inflammation, fibrosis, mucus production, and destruction of lung tissue, resulting in decreased lung elasticity and reduced surface area for gas exchange. [3]

Clinically, COPD is divided into two main types: emphysema and chronic bronchitis. The Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) classification further stratifies the severity of COPD based on spirometric parameters. The disease often coexists with other comorbidities, particularly cardiovascular diseases, which share common risk factors such as smoking and aging. The presence of these comorbidities can significantly impact the prognosis and management of COPD. [4] Acute exacerbations of COPD (AECOPD) are characterized by a sudden worsening of respiratory symptoms, often triggered by infections or environmental factors, and can lead to severe complications including increased cardiac stress and myocardial injury. Elevated cardiac biomarkers, such as troponin, during AECOPD episodes have been associated with higher mortality and adverse outcomes. [5] Understanding the relationship between cardiac biomarkers and COPD exacerbations is crucial for improving patient management and outcomes. [6,7]

Recent studies have highlighted the strong association between COPD and cardiovascular diseases, with COPD patients exhibiting a higher risk of myocardial damage. [8] This study aims to assess the levels of cardiac troponin-T in patients with acute exacerbation of COPD and to investigate its correlation with the severity of the disease.

Methodology

A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted at the National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research in Jaipur, Rajasthan, over a period of one and a half years, from July 1, 2022, to December 31, 2023. This single-center, observational, cross-sectional study included patients with COPD aged over 40 years who were admitted to the Department of General Medicine and Pulmonary Medicine.

The selection criteria were defined to include all known COPD patients above 40 years of age, of both genders, who were willing to participate in the study. Exclusion criteria were set to filter out patients with pre-existing hemodynamic instability, severe systemic illness, clinical evidence of myocardial infarction, congestive cardiac failure or cardiac arrest before admission, and myocarditis. The

purposive sampling technique was employed to select a sample size of 180, calculated using a standard formula with a prevalence rate of COPD-related hospitalization in Rajasthan set at 0.358 and a margin of error at 7%.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Scientific and Institute Ethics Committee before commencing the study. Patients were enrolled after obtaining written consent, and data was collected using a predesigned Performa covering demographics, clinical profiles, laboratory and radiological investigations, and spirometry findings. Laboratory investigations included CBC, ESR, ABG, TC, DC, Blood urea, Serum creatinine, and Cardiac Troponin T levels, measured on admission and 24 hours later using a quantitative ELISA assay. Radiological investigations involved Chest X-rays, ECG, and ECHO, if required.

Pulmonary function tests (PFT) were conducted using a computerized spirometer, measuring parameters such as Forced Vital Capacity (FVC), Forced Expiratory Volume in the first second (FEV1), Residual Volume (RV), Total Lung Capacity (TLC), and FEV1/FVC ratio. The spirometry parameters were recorded, and interpretation followed the global criteria for COPD diagnosis. Serum Troponin T levels above 0.04 µg/L were considered positive.

Statistical Analysis

Data compilation and analysis were performed using SPSS software version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used for qualitative data, and percentages/proportions for quantitative data. The t-test and Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient were employed to determine the correlation between cardiac Troponin T levels and the severity of COPD. A linear regression analysis was conducted to further explore these relationships, with statistical significance set at a p-value of less than 0.05.

Results

In this study, a total of 180 patients were assessed, revealing significant insights into the demographics and clinical characteristics of COPD patients. The gender distribution of the study population showed that 61.67% were male and 38.33% were female. The majority of the study participants were male, indicating a higher prevalence of COPD or its exacerbations among males in this population. (Table 1). The majority of participants were in the middle-aged group, specifically 41-50 years (31.11%), followed closely by those aged 31-40 years (29.44%). This suggests that COPD significantly affects individuals in their middle age, likely due to prolonged exposure to risk factors over time (Table 2).

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	111	61.67%
Female	69	38.33%

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Age (in years)

Age Interval (Years)	Frequency	Percent
20 – 30	18	10.00%
31 – 40	53	29.44%
41 – 50	56	31.11%
51 – 60	37	20.56%
61 – 70	16	8.89%

Religious affiliation among the patients showed that 82.78% were Hindu and 17.22% were Muslim, reflecting the demographic composition of Jaipur, Rajasthan, where the study was conducted. Occupational status revealed that housewives constituted the largest group (28.33%), followed by farmers (24.44%) and businessmen (15%). This indicates that COPD impacts individuals across various occupations, with notable effects on those engaged in domestic work and agriculture, likely due to exposure to indoor and outdoor air pollution. Residence distribution showed a significant majority of pa-

tients (84.44%) were from rural areas, with only 15.56% from urban areas. This highlights a higher prevalence or reporting of COPD in rural settings, possibly due to increased exposure to biomass smoke and limited access to healthcare facilities. Smoking habits were prevalent among the patients, with 81.11% having a history of smoking, of which 41.11% were current smokers and 40% were former smokers. These underscores smoking as a major risk factor for COPD, with a significant number of patients continuing to smoke despite their diagnosis (Table 3).

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Smoking Habits among Subjects

Smoking Habits	Frequency	Percent
Never Smoke	34	18.89%
Current Smoker	74	41.11%
Former Smoker	72	40.00%

Alcohol abuse was less prevalent, with 86.11% of patients reporting they never consumed alcohol, while 13.89% admitted to drinking either daily or intermittently. Clinically, diabetes mellitus was the most common comorbidity (27.22%), followed by hypertension (22.22%), obesity (19.44%), atrial fibrillation (11.67%), ischemic heart disease (10.56%), and a history of previous myocardial infarction (8.89%). The presence of these comorbidities suggests a complex interplay between COPD and other chronic conditions, contributing to the overall disease burden. Physical examination revealed that 11.67% of patients exhibited clubbing/cyanosis, 11.11% had pallor, 9.44% had icterus, and 4.44% had lymphadenopathy. Baseline clinical parameters showed that 94.44% of patients

had a normal pulse rate (60-90 beats per minute), with a mean pulse rate of 74.35 ± 10.20 beats per minute. Respiratory rate analysis indicated that 92.22% of patients were tachypnoeic, with a mean respiratory rate of 26.28 ± 2.69 breaths per minute. Blood urea levels were elevated in 29.44% of patients, with a mean level of 18.68 ± 4.28 mg/dl, while 17.22% had elevated serum creatinine levels (>1.10 mg/dl), with a mean of 0.933 ± 0.164 mg/dl. Troponin T levels were elevated (>0.04 ng/dl) in 60% of patients, with a mean level of 0.048 ± 0.021 ng/dl, indicating potential cardiac involvement in these patients (Table 4). Elevated ESR levels were observed in 80.56% of patients, with a mean ESR of 28.39 ± 7.97 mm/hr.

Table 4: Frequency Distribution of Troponin T of Patients

Troponin T Levels (ng/dl)	Frequency	Percent
0 - 0.02	21	11.67%
0.021 - 0.040	51	28.33%
0.041 - 0.060	48	26.67%
0.061 - 0.080	50	27.78%
0.081 - 0.100	10	5.56%

Table 5: Frequency Distribution of FEV1 of Patients

FEV1 (%)	Frequency	Percent
31 - 40	8	4.44%
41 - 50	13	7.22%
51 - 60	61	33.89%
61 - 70	40	22.22%
71 - 80	45	25.00%
81 - 90	13	7.22%

Table 6: Frequency Distribution of FEV1/FVC of Patients

FEV1/FVC Ratio	Frequency	Percent
≤ 0.40	55	30.56%
0.41 - 0.50	40	22.22%
0.51 - 0.60	29	16.11%
0.61 - 0.70	47	26.11%
0.71 - 0.80	9	5.00%

Pulmonary function tests revealed that 67.78% of patients had reduced FEV1 (<70%), with a mean FEV1 of $63.35 \pm 12.15\%$. The majority of COPD patients had significantly reduced FEV1 values, reflecting the severity of airway obstruction in this population (Table 5). Additionally, 95% of patients had a reduced FEV1/FVC ratio (<0.70), with a mean ratio of 0.495 ± 0.153 . The FEV1/FVC ratio further confirms the severe airflow limitation among the majority of COPD patients, which is a hallmark of the disease (Table 6). Correlation analysis showed that FEV1 and FEV1/FVC were significantly negatively correlated with Troponin T levels ($r = -0.644$, $p = 0.00001$ and $r = -0.56$, $p = 0.00001$, respectively), suggesting that higher Troponin T levels are associated with more severe pulmonary impairment.

Regression analysis further confirmed a negative correlation between FEV1 and Troponin T, as well as between FEV1/FVC and Troponin T, indicating that elevated Troponin T levels can serve as a marker for early diagnosis and assessment of severity in acute exacerbations of COPD. This study concludes that elevated serum levels of Cardiac Troponin T are significantly associated with the severity of acute exacerbation of COPD, emphasizing the importance of cardiac monitoring in these patients for better management and prognostic evaluation.

Discussion

During the study period, 180 patients were analyzed. The study had a male predominance, with 61.67% of the subjects being male. Most of the subjects were middle-aged, particularly in the age group of 41-50 years, which constituted 31.11% of the participants. The mean age of the subjects was 44.38 ± 10.50 years. These findings are in line with similar studies conducted by deFilippi CR (2010) [9] and Eggers KM (2013) [10], which also indicated that COPD increases the risk of cardiac damage in older male patients. In the study by Koppad

A et al. (2023) [11], the average age of patients with elevated cardiac troponin was 59 ± 7.5 years, whereas the average age of patients with negative cTnI was 60.5 ± 7.2 years. Consistent with this observation, Baillard C et al. (2018) [12] found no significant age-related difference between patients with positive and negative cTnI.

In our study, a significant proportion of the patients, 81.11%, were smokers. Out of these, 41.11% were current smokers, indicating a high prevalence of smoking among the study population. The most common comorbidities observed were diabetes mellitus (27.22%), hypertension (22.22%), and obesity (19.44%). These findings are consistent with the research by Antonelli Incalzi R et al. (1997) [13], which also reported a high frequency of cardiac comorbidities due to smoking, hypertension, and diabetes. The study by Deveci F et al. (2006) [14] found that smoking affects cardiac troponin levels, although no significant statistical difference was observed.

Higher Troponin T levels (>0.04 ng/dl) were observed in 60% of the patients in our study, with a mean Troponin T level of 0.048 ± 0.021 . Elevated ESR levels were seen in 80.56% of the patients, with a mean ESR of 28.39 ± 7.97 . These findings support the assertion by Neukamm MA et al. (2013) [15] that troponin levels rise when the myocardium is under stress or ischemia. The evidence suggests that COPD patients have higher baseline levels of highly sensitive cTnT compared to the general population.

Pulmonary function assessment showed that 92.22% of the patients had tachypnea, indicating a high rate of fast breathing. Additionally, 67.78% of the patients had an FEV1 (forced expiratory volume in one second) of less than 70%, with a mean FEV1 of 63.35 ± 12.15 . Only 5% of the patients had a normal FEV1/FVC (forced vital capacity) ratio (>0.70), while 95% had a lower ratio with a mean FEV1/FVC ratio of 0.495 ± 0.153 . The spi-

rometry parameters, FEV1 and FEV1/FVC were found to be significantly negatively correlated with Troponin T levels ($r = -0.644$, $p=0.00001$ and $r=-0.59$, $p=0.00001$), indicating that higher Troponin T levels are associated with worse pulmonary function. According to Raouf S et al. (1999) [16] found that mechanical ventilation is essential for patients with respiratory failure or shock, as it affects right ventricular function. They observed a negative correlation between FEV1 and Troponin T, indicating that higher Troponin T levels can help early diagnose acute exacerbation of COPD.

The linear regression analysis was done between FEV1 with Troponin T among study subjects. Finding revealed that there is a negatively correlation between FEV1/FVC with Troponin T among these study patients. By observing above finding indicate that an increase in Troponin T levels correlates with changes in FEV1/FVC, helping to diagnose worsening COPD. Hattori K et al. (2015) [17] also showed that higher hs-cTnT is associated with

lower FVC, FEV1% predicted, and %DLco/VA suggesting that lung inflammation in COPD can affect the heart. Among patients with varying FEV1 levels, Troponin T was elevated in a significant number, with the association between Troponin T and COPD severity being statistically significant ($p=0.00962$). This demonstrates a clear correlation between Cardiac Troponin T levels and the severity of acute exacerbation of COPD.

As shown in the current research by Koppad A et al. (2023)¹¹, 42.2% of patients with AECOPD had high cardiac troponin levels (above 0.01 ng/mL). Although the frequency of cTnT elevation has varied, as indicated in the table below, the result that raised cardiac troponins occur in patients with acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is consistent with several studies documented. To compare the Incidence of Elevated Troponin in Patients with Acute Exacerbation in various studies with present study:

Author and year of publication	Incidence of cardiac troponin elevation
Baillard et al. (2003) [18]	18%
Martins et al. (2009) [19]	70%
Hoiseith et al. (2011) [20]	74%
Brekke et al. (2009) [21]	27%
Chang et al. (2011) [22]	16.6%
Present study	27%

There is a high risk of myocardial infarction within a few days of a COPD exacerbation, according to study findings of, and there is evidence of cardiac dysfunction in the initial stage of an exacerbation of the disease. Previous findings of worsening arterial stiffness (measured by aortic pulse wave velocity) over several days from the onset of the exacerbation support this hypothesis. Patel AR et al. (2013) [23] and Donaldson GC et al. (2010) [24].

This study's merits lie in the fact that it documents for the first time the link between COPD patients' serum connection with cardiac Troponin T and acute exacerbation. However, there are a number of caveats to this research.

Conclusion

The study assessed cardiac Troponin-T levels and their correlation with the severity of acute exacerbations in COPD patients at the National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research in Jaipur. Most participants were middle-aged, predominantly male, and from rural backgrounds, with an average age of 44 years. This demographic trend highlights the considerable impact of COPD on the middle-aged population. Clinically, a large number of patients exhibited comorbid conditions, including diabetes mellitus, hypertension, obesity, atrial fibrillation, and ischemic heart disease. Additionally, a substantial proportion of the cohort were current

or former smokers, emphasizing the critical role of smoking in the development and exacerbation of COPD. The study's primary focus on cardiac Troponin-T levels revealed that a significant percentage of COPD patients had elevated Troponin-T levels above the normal range. These elevated levels were strongly associated with increased severity of COPD exacerbations, as evidenced by the spirometry parameters. Specifically, there was a notable negative correlation between Troponin-T levels and both FEV1 and FEV1/FVC ratios, indicating that higher Troponin-T levels corresponded to worse lung function and more severe disease exacerbations. The statistical analysis further confirmed that patients with elevated Troponin-T levels were more likely to require assisted ventilation, underscoring the prognostic significance of this biomarker in acute COPD exacerbations. The study concludes that cardiac Troponin-T is a valuable marker for assessing the severity of acute exacerbations in COPD patients. Elevated Troponin-T levels can aid in the early diagnosis and management of these patients, potentially improving clinical outcomes and providing a clearer understanding of the interplay between cardiac stress and pulmonary function in COPD exacerbations. This study emphasizes the need for further research to explore the mechanisms underlying this relationship and to

develop targeted interventions for better management of COPD exacerbations.

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